

1 **CXCL9 and CXCL12 are activated in the lung in human COPD.**

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6 Pulmonary diseases of the lower respiratory tract including emphysema and COPD are a leading cause of
7 death in humans. Description of the transcriptional landscape within which the disease entity operates
8 permits development of novel therapeutics and therapeutic strategies. We describe here induction of
9 chemokines CXCL9 and CXCL12 in the lungs of humans with COPD. In the lungs, CXCL9 was
10 co-regulated with CCL4, a chemokine ligand whose induction in the lung we recently described. The data
11 point to a pathological setting centered on tissue damage resulting from an inflammatory loop whose
12 major salient features are induction of IL-1 β and TNF α , indicating cytokine and chemokine based
13 intervention strategies will be viable in re-establishing homeostasis in the lung.
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